

Concepts of Transformational Leadership, Self-efficacy, and Employee Engagement on Employee Performance

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to review previous articles, looking for relationships between variables. This study is a literature review, does not involve data processing, and does not have a research sample. The conclusion of this study is that there is a relationship between the variables observed in previous research, which supports the review of the literature in this article. What is new in this article is that no one has taken into account all the independent variables of the addict. The number of important articles allows the article to become a reference for further research and quantitative developments.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important assets of a company is its human resources because they affect the survival of the company. The form and goals of the organization are created based on various visions for the benefit of humanity in achieving its mission, governed and managed by humans. Thus, people are a strategic element in all organizational activities. Organizations must realize the potential of their workforce as the business environment becomes increasingly competitive profit. Employee performance is influenced by many factors, internal and external. The factors themselves are knowledge, skills and possessed skills, work motivation, personality, attitudes, and behaviors that influence performance. These factors themselves are beyond, including leadership. style of superiors, relationships between employees, and the work environment in which employees work. Employee performance can be evaluated using several indicators such as quality the employee's amount of work, the amount or achievement of identified goals, identified tasks, the employee's responsibilities for assigned work, and how the employee takes care of themselves there. The basic coefficients of performance that can be used to measure performance are 1. Quality is the degree to which the process or result achieved when performing activities reaches a level of perfection or reaches an expected level target. 2. Quantity is the quantity produced production, i.e... the number of rupees, units, and operating cycles completed. 3.. Profitability, which is a part of secondary research is carried out by studying the use of organizational resources, and theoretical foundations related to research (people, resources main, technology, and material) to maximize to achieve the highest results or reduce losses per unit of electricity used. 4. Monitoring need is the degree to which personnel employee performs job functions without the supervision of a supervisor to prevent unwanted actions. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Wau & Purwanto, 2021); (Sari et al., 2021); (Abdelmegeed Abdelwahed et al., 2022); (Chon & Zoltan, 2019); (Canavesi & Minelli, 2022); (Ángeles López-Cabarcos et al., 2022).

Employee performance is the results an employee achieves in his or her work according to certain criteria applicable to a specific job. Employee performance is a function of the interaction between ability and motivation. In the study of performance management of workers or employees, certain factors should be considered important because the performance of each employee in the organization is a part of the organization's performance and can determine organizational performance. The success or failure of employee performance achieved by the organization will be affected. according to the performance level of each employee and group. Performance is organizational behavior directly related to the production of goods or provision of services. Performance is often thought of as the accomplishment of tasks, with the term task coming from thinking about the activities required of workers, with the term competency having a broader meaning. Performance includes aspects of effort, loyalty, potential, leadership, and work ethics. Competence is considered in three aspects, which are: the behavior that a person exhibits at work, the actual results or results achieved by employees, and the evaluation of factors

such as motivation drive and commitment, initiative, leadership potential, and spirit in the workplace. Related to organizational goals such as quality, efficiency and other performance criteria. Performance reflects the degree and extent to which an individual's job requirements are met According to the above definition, performance is considered both qualitative and quantitative outcomes. The performance success or failure achieved by an organization is influenced by the level of individual and collective performance. Because performance outcomes are measured with instruments developed in research studies, they depend on general performance measures, which are then translated into basic behavioral assessments that may include many factors, including the quantity of work, quality of work, opinions or statements, decisions made when performing work and job description. To measure individual performance, there are a number of indicators, performance indicators commonly used to evaluate individual employee performance, Knowledge, skills and abilities/skills Work competencies, Work attitude, demonstrated by enthusiasm, dedication, and motivation, Quality of work.

Interaction, such as communication skills and the ability to interact with other team members working team. What determines the success or failure of a company is the performance of its employees. If employee performance is good, the company can achieve its goals faster, but if employee performance is poor, the opposite will happen. With such performance, the company must improve and maintain employee performance. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Al Hazman & Achmadi, 2021); (Armstrong, 2009); (Prasetyo et al., 2021); (Cachón-Rodríguez et al., 2022); (Safitri, 2019); (Nuraeni et al., 2022); (Riwukore et al., 2022).

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is a leadership style used by leaders to motivate and empower those they are responsible for working together to achieve the company's vision. Ultimately, transformational leadership is a form of values, beliefs, and a need to embrace change as a new form of leadership. disruption A leader with a transformational leadership style is said to be able to influence the overall performance of employees. A leader who adopts a transformational leadership style is often visionary and can also help employees or subordinates perfect necessary skills. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Nur Kholifah & Aidil Fadli, 2022); (Bakhtiar, 2019); (Nur Kholifah & Aidil Fadli, 2022); (Ulfa, 2013).

Transformational leadership is a modern leadership style, suitable for current developments. Here are some reasons why companies need this type of leadership: A person with transformational leadership becomes a role model or role model for employees Of course, this will help employees feel motivated and grow according to their model, so they can increase productivity and take the company forward at the same time. Transformational leadership is a leadership style that emphasizes closeness and deep connection. So that

employees feel no distance from superiors. This will of course ensure good communication and being able to work efficiently and effectively. A leader with transformational leadership ability is not rigid and always wants to innovate. The manager is not afraid to express opinions that, in his opinion, can contribute to progress and company development. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Susanto, Widyastuti, Karsono, et al., 2023); (Susanto, Agusinta, & Setyawati, 2023); (F. A. Putri & Muhdiyanto, 2018); (M. D. Putri & Soedarsono, 2017); (JUNAIDAH, 2016).

A transformational leadership approach encourages, inspires, and motivates employees to innovate and create the change needed to shape the company's future success. This is achieved by setting an example at the management level through authenticity, a strong sense of corporate culture, employee ownership, and independence in the workplace. Transformational leaders are agents of change within the business, able to identify trends in innovation and technological change, and then help the organization adopt these changes. Transformational leaders inspire and motivate their people without micromanaging they trust trained employees to make decisions within the scope of work assigned to them. It's a management style designed to give employees more room to be creative, look to the future, and find new solutions to old problems. Employees who are on a leadership path will also be prepared to become transformational leaders through mentoring and training. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Qammar & Abidin, 2020); (Rahmah, 2013); (Llorens et al., 2018); (Naeem & Nawaz, 2017).

Self-efficacy

The self-confidence that each person has is very influential on the results obtained after they complete their work. When doing something, people who from the beginning have confidence that they can complete the task smoothly will find it easier to do so. This self-confidence is known as self-efficacy. Self-efficacy indicators there are three indicators that exist in self-efficacy, namely: Level of task difficulty (Magnitude) This indicator relates to the level of difficulty of the task given. Each individual will have a different level of self-efficacy in simple, medium, or very difficult tasks. Generalization This index concerns how well individuals can relate to previous tasks and experiences when faced with a new task or job, whereas a person with high self-efficacy will persist in increasing their efforts despite experiences that weaken them. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Hugten et al., 2023); (Borg et al., 2023); (Sommovigo et al., 2023); (X. Wang et al., 2022); (Lestari et al., 2020).

Some factors that influence self-efficacy are Experience performing previous tasks. A person is more confident that they can succeed in a task when they have been successful in that task or a similar task messages from others. Appreciation from others can motivate and instill confidence in someone so that they are more confident in completing their tasks. The successes and failures of others a person often tends to consider the successes and failures of his friends. When she sees friends with similar abilities succeeding in completing tasks, she

becomes optimistic about her own success. Self-efficacy is a person's internal belief in their own abilities, that they have the ability to do something or overcome a situation, or that they will succeed in doing so. self-efficacy is people's belief in their ability to produce levels of performance and master situations that affect their lives, self-efficacy will also determine how people feel, think, motivate, and behave. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Pulungan & Rivai, 2021); (Dewi Wijayanti & Supartha, 2019); (Ghayour Baghbani et al., 2023); (Audenaert et al., 2021); (Yener et al., 2021); (Ni et al., 2022).

People with a high sense of self-efficacy: Develop a deeper interest in the activities in which they participate. Develop a stronger sense of and commitment to interests and activities Recover quickly from setbacks, setbacks, and disappointments View problems as opportunities, challenges, and tasks to be mastered People with low self-efficacy: Avoid tasks Difficult and challenging tasks Believe that difficult tasks and situations are beyond their abilities always look to personal failures and negative outcomes Quickly lose faith in personal abilities. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Nurfajar et al., 2018); (Setyawan & Bagis, 2021); (Tanjung et al., 2020); (Pauzi et al., 2022); (Susanto, Hidayat, Widyastuti, et al., 2023).

Employee Engagement

According to (Hornyak et al., 2022) Employee engagement is a term in the field of human resources that originates from English. If translated literally, it means employee engagement. In fact, employee engagement measures their commitment to their job, company, and organizational goals. This engagement is considered important because employees who feel actively involved and committed to the company tend to be more productive, more enthusiastic, and stay with the company longer (Mikalef et al., 2023).

Increasing Employee Engagement, Increasing employee engagement is a long-term plan that must be implemented in a systematic and measurable manner. Three ways to improve it are:

1. Communicate deeply and openly, Implementing strong and open interactions will promote trust between colleagues as well as between employees and managers, as long as the communication topics discussed are related or unrelated to each other, of course, quit. Examples of what can be done: Organize regular meetings between management and employees to discuss issues related to work or business operations. Create accessible and responsive communication channels, such as Slack forums or internal company groups that allow employees to ask questions and open communication. Provide special forms for types of discussions that cannot be discussed openly, such as job satisfaction surveys or feedback forms that are only available to employee managers innovation is accessible.
2. Reward positive contributions and recognize employees who are doing good work, providing rewards and development opportunities can have

a positive impact on motivation and employee satisfaction, which helps increase productivity and overall organizational performance. Examples of what can be done: Give direct feedback with positive words or praise in an open forum. Reward outstanding performers at regular events of the company or offer incentives such as bonuses, salary increases, or special benefits. Keep numbers 4 - 1 meeting to discuss work improvement or an employee making a mistake that needs to be fixed immediately.

3. Opportunities for personal transformation. In an era of competition In an increasingly fierce business environment, creating these opportunities also helps companies retain excellent employees and encourage them to continuously improve, improve your skills and knowledge. Examples of what can be done: Provide continuing education and skills development, both directly related to work and more general. Carry out projects that challenge questions and create opportunities to innovate and contribute to the growth of the company. business goals. Build a clear career plan and create opportunities for advancement and continuous salary increases. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Pringgabayu & Dewi, 2018); (Suikkanen, 2010); (Song et al., 2022); (Guan & Frenkel, 2019); (Guest, 2014); (Muhammad & Tahir, 2023); (Zhou et al., 2022); (Shuck & Wollard, 2010); (Handoyo & Setiawan, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

This type of research is a type of qualitative research, specifically data that is raw material that needs to be reprocessed to produce information or insights, both qualitative and quantitative data Quantity shows the truth. This study used a literature review to systematically examine previous articles to see how they correlated with current research. The results show the relationship between all the independent variables and the dependent variable. In human resource management research, there is no research framework similar to this article, and the hypotheses of this study are rare in previous studies.

RESULTS

Employee performance is the result of work that can be performed by a group of people in an organization with their respective authority and responsibility. Within an organization with its respective powers and responsibilities, in order to achieve the objectives of the concerned organization in a lawful manner, without violating the law, without violating rules and regulations. To achieve the objectives of the relevant organization in a lawful, legal, and ethical manner, that is consistent with ethics and morality. Performance in the sense of work performance is something done or a product or service produced or provided by a person or group of people produced or supplied by a person or group of persons. Performance in the sense of job performance is the process of measuring and evaluating a person's level of success in activities and the results that can be achieved. one's success in one's activities and the results one can achieve or demonstrate in the performance of one's duties. someone is performing work duties. It can also be said that the

employee's work result is the performance or appearance of the employee in performing his or her job. Employees can be said to have good job performance when they can perform their jobs well, meaning they achieve previously set work goals or standards or can exceed the standards, predetermined. Employee performance is influenced by a number of factors, including motivation, work environment conditions, relationships with co-workers, abilities, and past experiences. Every company always wants to achieve maximum goal, these goals can be achieved if the employee's performance is good. For this reason, the company tries to motivate or encourage good-performing employees by providing them with rewards, opportunities for success, more meaningful work, job security, and good policies company's job book. Employee performance is the output of work that an individual or a group of people in an organization can perform, in accordance with his or her authority and responsibilities, to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally without violating morality or ethics Factors that influence employee performance are: 1. Efficiency and effectiveness A team's effectiveness depends on its ability to achieve goals according to planned needs, while effectiveness functions Note the level of sacrifice to achieve the goal. 2. Responsibility, Responsibility is an inseparable part and therefore belongs to this agency. 3. Discipline, Discipline generally includes compliance with applicable laws and regulations. Meanwhile, employee discipline is the employee's compliance with the labor contract with the company where he works. 4) Initiative A person's initiative involves the power of thinking, and creativity in the form of ideas that reflect something related to the organization's goals.

DISCUSSION

Employee performance is an integral part of the scope of the organization, the company, and all its stakeholders. Employee performance also plays an important role as a standard for evaluating employee quality to maintain the productivity of all employees working in the company. If an employee is evaluated as doing a good job, that employee has the right to receive appreciation or other forms of reward from the company. Employee Performance Indicators and Interpretation, Employee Performance Indicators are tools to measure how well employees achieve company goals and how employees contribute to the company's success. Here are some employee performance indicators and their explanations:

1. Job Quality, Job Quality Measures how well an employee can perform his or her job and meet standards. established standards. Indicators of work quality include punctuality, accuracy in performing tasks and quality of products created.
2. Labor Productivity, Labor productivity measures how effectively employees do their work and how many results they can produce in a given time. Labor productivity indicators include the volume of production or sales, the number of tasks completed in a given time, and the effective use of time and resources.

3. Participation at work, Workplace engagement measures how often employees are present at work according to a set work schedule. Signs of work engagement include absenteeism, tardiness, and vacation time.
4. Labor discipline measures the level of compliance with the rules and procedures set by the enterprise by employees. Indicators of labor discipline include compliance with rules and regulations. rules and procedures set by the enterprise. Work schedules, rules, workplace safety, and procedures for using working tools and equipment.
5. Teamwork, Teamwork measures the extent to which employees work with other team members to achieve common goals. Teamwork indicators include communication skills, the ability to solve problems together, and the ability to contribute to achieving team goals.
6. Innovation, Innovation measures employee creativity and innovation as they come up with new ideas to improve business performance. Indicators of innovation include the ability to think creatively, the ability to generate new ideas, and the ability to apply new ideas to daily work. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Zen et al., 2023); (Primadi Candra Susanto et al., 2023); (Setyawati et al., 2022); (Susanto, Sawitri, Ali, et al., 2023); (Susanto, Sawitri, & Suroso, 2023); (Sawitri et al., 2019); (Chiniara & Bentein, 2016); (Susanto, Sawitri, & Susita, 2023); (Kyndt et al., 2009); (Kumar & Kumra, 2022; Tasgin & Dilek, 2023); (Xie et al., 2020); (J. Wang et al., 2023).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Improving Employee Performance, here are five tips that can help improve employee performance in the workplace: Provide Training and Development Providing training and development is an effective way to improve employee performance. By training, employees can improve their knowledge, skills and abilities to perform their duties better. Companies can also provide career development opportunities for their employees to help them achieve higher career goals.
2. Providing constructive feedback, Providing constructive feedback to employees can help them improve future performance. Feedback must be objective, clear and specific so that employees can fully understand what needs improvement.
3. Building a positive feedback work culture Building a positive work culture help increase employee motivation and performance. A positive work culture includes values such as cooperation, mutual respect, honesty and integrity. Companies can create a positive work culture by providing good role models from management and company leadership.
4. Improving the Quality of Work Life, Improving the Quality of Life live Work, direct work of employees can help improve their performance. workers' lives by providing them with adequate working facilities such as comfortable workplace, tools Modern and safe working in the workplace. good work Companies can also help their employees balance work, life and personal life.

5. Develop a common work plan, Develop a common work plan can help improve employee performance. employees develop clear work goals and strategies. In this way, Employees will be more motivated to achieve the goals set for themselves and can clearly understand the tasks that need to be completed. It is important for employees to know their job performance because it will help them know whether their job performance is good or bad, employees can also evaluate themselves and find out the areas where they need to improve efficiency.

Additionally, companies can provide constructive feedback and help employees improve their performance in the future. Employee performance can also help companies in the process of evaluating employees and making decisions regarding promotions, incentives or layoffs. Consistent with the research of previous researchers and experts (Chan et al., 2017); (Ancona & Caldwell, 2015); (Braglia et al., 2022); (Abu Oda et al., 2022); (Joppen et al., 2019); (Susanto, Agusinta, & Setyawati, 2023); (Syahputra & Susanto, 2022); (Abdelwahed et al., 2022); (Chaaban et al., 2023); (Deci & Ryan, 2000); (Parmenter, 2015).

FURTHER STUDY

To achieve the research objective, the variables of this study, which are believed to have a positive influence, are highlighted by presenting scientific results, and this scientific article reinforces these results. Current search results use search variables as search objects. Scientific article, we see that there are a number of other variables that can be used in more in-depth or in-depth research.

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